

Fragments III & a 3rd Manichaean Harmony
by Brian Paul Kaess

1. 'I shall teach you as Jesus did to Little Ones.'

Now, you will behold the mystery most lucidly and magnificently¹. These even the angels cannot hide. Mani was protected by the might of the angels and their powers of holiness. They nourished me with visions and signs that came to me as a flash of lightning. When witnessed, I remained in silence. I no longer followed the Law of the Baptists.

So, the Date-Palm tree threatened revenge if it were cut down, not unlike Callimachus' tale of that tree in the sacred grove of a sanctuary of Demeter (presumably that in Cnidus)². Mani was guarded by the mighty power of the Light angels, whose only command was Jesus. And the Twin spoke: "Strengthen your power, make your mind firm, and receive all that is about to be revealed to you." My lord Mani said thus: "Just as nowadays a young horse, used by a king, becomes the king's mount through the capability of the horse trainers, So that he ` might sit upon it in honor and glory and carry out his particular [task], in this same way the mind possesses the body, in order to do good for mankind. . . . he might free the souls from ignorance by becoming the Paraclete (Holy Spirit or Helper)

In this generation Mani (216-274 CE, died age 58³) saw a mirror image of himself. It was in this year that Dariardaxar the King of Persia, subdued the city Atra (circa 240 CE). Mani was 24 years old. The Mani codex recounts that Mani's father joined the Elchasaites, a Jewish-Christian sect, after the "storming of Atra," a city in Mesopotamia. Mani said: 'The most blessed Lord was greatly moved with compassion for me, called me into his grace, and immediately sent to me from there my Twin.' When my Father was pleased and had mercy and compassion on me, to ransom (me) from the error of the Sectarrians, I thereafter took counsel. I believed in the best hope and redemption for those who suffer patiently⁴. Jesus revealed to me his boundless heights and unfathomable depths. The Lord was a good and excellent counselor. He is all-glorious and all-blessed. This mystery I have revealed to you.

Let us marvel beyond measure at these mysteries. The Lacunae in our soul was deep, but Jesus filled it with grace. Though I am solitary and poor, I was able to reveal this mystery. Though we stand alone in the midst of the multitude, we may yet measure up. And again, he disclosed the womb of the pillar, the Fathers, and the mightiest powers which are hidden. And secret things. I fell down before him and said: 'These things which I ask from you are given to me and will remain with me at all times, not hidden but [clearly] manifested through [my] hands [. . .] to [all] eyes.' Now the souls of the victors may be seen.

¹ See *The Cologne Mani Codex* "Concerning the Origin of His Body," edited and translated by Ron Cameron and Arthur J. Dewey (New York, 1979),

² See "Thou Shalt not Kill a Tree': Greek, Manichaean and Indian Tales," *Bulletin of the American Society of Papyrologists* 16 (1979) 85-108.

³ Mani was 58 when he died, the same age as myself when writing this account. Perhaps I will pick up where Mani left off.

⁴ See Plato's *Republic* Book IX, around 583–587 where 'to be patient under suffering is best' is emphasized.

May He impart forgiveness of trespasses and accusations to your Elect. For it is through the signs of the truth that those of the lie are nullified. Now he revealed to me mysteries hidden to the world, which are not permitted for anyone to see or hear. He came to me and became solitary in our very midst. He said: 'Know, then, brothers, and understand all these things written herein.'

And then the Paraclete (Holy Ghost) spoke: "These alone have written about the rapture of their teacher in order to boast." For let the one who is willing hear... the revelation from the Elect. Praise and extol your teachers and the truth and hope which was revealed. And once more: "I am Balsamos, the greatest angel of light. Wherefore take and write these things which I reveal to you on most pure papyrus, incorruptible and insusceptible." In a vision he noted very great was the glory about him. "I opened my eyes and beheld before my face [an angel], whose [splendor I] was not able to speak. And there before me were flashes of lightning. When I listened to these things, my heart rejoiced and my mind was changed, and I became like one of the greatest angels. When that angel placed his hand on my right hand, he wrenched me from the world which I was born and carried me off to another place exceedingly 'great. Now I heard behind me a very great uproar from those angels whom I left behind. And there was revealed very great mysteries of majesty.

Again in the Apocalypse of Enosh it reads thus: "In the third year, on the tenth month, I went out for a walk into the desert land, reflecting in my mind about heaven and earth and [about all] the works and [things]—by what reason [they have come into being] and by whose [will] they exist. . ."

"Death snatched me up with very great Silence. My heart became heavy, all my limbs trembled, my backbone was shaken violently, and my feet did not stand on their pins. I went away to many flat plains and saw there extremely high mountains. The Spirit snatched me up and carried me off to the mountain in silent power. There many great [visions] were revealed to me."

Now he spoke with me and said: 'He who is eminently most powerful sent me to you so that I may reveal to you the secrets which ' you pondered, since you were singled out for the truth. Now all these things that are hidden, write upon bronze tablets and store them up in the desert land. All that you write, write most clearly. For this revelation [of mine, which never] dies, is revealed to our brothers and sisters of our faith. So we write this down in the spirit of truth.

"Another voice blew a breath of life into my face and brought an increase in [my] power and glory." "I am Enoch, the just. Great is my distress and there is an outpouring of tears from my eyes, because I have heard the reproach which came from the mouth of the impious." Now he was saying: "With tears in my eyes and a prayer on my lips, I beheld standing before me [seven] angels [coming down from] heaven."

One of the angels, Michael by name, said to me: 'For this reason I have been sent to you, so that we may point out to you all the works and reveal to you the realm of the pious, and that I may show you the realm of the impious and what the place of punishment of the lawless is like.' "They set me on a chariot of-wind and carried me off to the ends of the heavens." [We] passed through the worlds, the world [of death] and the world of [darkness] and the world of fire. After these things they brought me into an extremely rich world, which was most glorious in its light, more splendid than the luminaries which I saw." He beheld everything and carefully questioned the angels; and whatever they said to him, he would inscribe in his writings.

Likewise, we know that the apostle Paul was snatched up to the third heaven, just as he says in his Letter to the Galatians: "Paul an apostle—not from men nor [through] man, but through [Jesus] Christ and God the Father, who [raised] him from the [dead]." And He in the second Letter to the Corinthians says: "I shall go on to visions and revelations of the Lord. I know a man in Christ—whether in the body or out of the body I do not know, God knows—that this one was snatched up into Paradise and heard secret words which are not permitted for a man to utter. About such a one I shall boast, but about myself I shall not boast."

Now while he was outside of himself, and] snatched up into the third heaven and into Paradise, he both saw and heard, and it is this very thing that he recorded in riddles about his rapture and apostleship for the fellow initiates of the mysteries. The living hope was revealed to him for proclamation. Blessed be the all-praiseworthy apostle Mani!

We must interpret this to all posterity, to those householders of faith and their spiritual offspring, while we pass through these limpid waters. May his rapture and revelation be known. For in comparison to us, he was the Paraclete of Truth.

In a letter to Edessa he says thus: "The Truth and the secrets which I speak about—and the laying on of hands which is in my possession—not from men have I received it nor from fleshly creatures, not even from studies in the Scriptures. But when my most blessed Father, who called me into his grace, beheld me, since he did not [wish] me [and] the rest who are [in the] world to perish, he felt compassion, so that [he] might extend [his] well-being to those prepared to be chosen by him from the sects." Therefore, it is by grace he pulled me from the counsel of the many. He revealed to me the secret of his undefiled Father and that of the cosmos. How, at the beginning of time, the groundworks of both Good and Evil, were laid.

And Mani spoke: "I, Mani, an apostle of Jesus Christ through the will of God, the Father of Truth, from whom I also was born, who lives and abides forever, existing before all and also abiding after all. All things which are and will be subsist through his power. For from this very one I was begotten; and I am from his will. From him all that is true was revealed to me; Also, I am from [his] truth. [The truth of ages which he revealed] I have seen, and (that) truth I have disclosed to my fellow travelers; peace I have announced to the children of peace, hope I have proclaimed to the immortal race. The Elect I have chosen and. a path to the height I have shown to those who ascend according to this truth. Hope I have proclaimed and this revelation I have revealed. This immortal Gospel I have written, including in it these eminent mysteries, and disclosing in it the greatest works..."

So let there be true visions and glorious revelations. The gifts of the father are very great and rich. Let us establish His Wisdom as sufficient for the entire world. Let him send his unailing Twin, the entire fruit of immortality. The best redemption is hope, based on true instructions. Let there be laying on of hands. We revel in the rapture of the apostleship. The Paraclete, the spirit of Truth, is with us. We believe in the vision of the apostle Mani, whose commission he God gave. For in the 25th year of Mani's life, the Holy Spirit was revealed magnificently to him.

For, while he was still in that sect of the Baptists, he was like a lamb dwelling in a strange flock, or like a bird living with other birds of a different song, always with wisdom and skill he dwelt in their midst during all that time; None of them recognized him as to who he [was], or what he had received, or what had been revealed to him. Rather, they regarded him among themselves in this manner, according to the estimate of the Body.

The lord (Mani) said: "When I was dwelling in their midst, one day Sitaios, the elder of their council, the boss of Gara, took me by the hand, because he greatly loved me and regarded me as a beloved son. He took [me], then, by the hand—no one else was with us—and went and dug up and showed me very great treasures, which he kept secretly buried. He said to me: 'These treasures are mine and I have control of them. From now on they will be yours. For I love no one else like you, (and) to you I shall give these treasures.' When he had thus spoken to me I said in my heart: My most blessed Father preferred me and has given to me an immortal treasure which does not pass away."

"(Mani) spoke to him: "What good, then, are these treasures to me, which introduce sins and offenses to everyone who acquires them? For the treasure of God is very great and exceedingly rich and will bring everyone who inherits it to life." And he lay there astonished.

Then he showed those the path of holiness. Mani said: "Now when I destroyed and put to nought their words and their mysteries, demonstrating to them that they had not received these things which they pursue from the commandments of the Savior."

The purity, then, which was spoken about, is that which comes through knowledge, a separation of light from darkness, of death from life, of living waters from turbid, that [you] may know [that] each one is one and not another. As well as the commandments of the Savior, so that you might redeem the soul from annihilation. They began marveling at me, praised me and regarded me as a leader and teacher.

Some of them were saying: 'A living word is uttered by him; let us make him a teacher of our doctrine.' Others were saying: 'Has a voice really spoken to him in secret and does he say those things which it revealed to him?' Some were saying: 'Did something appear to him in a dream and does he say that which he saw?'

Others of them were filled with jealousy and rage, some of whom were voting for his death. Others were saying: 'He is the enemy of our Law.' Some [were saying]: '[He] wishes to go to the Gentiles and eat [Greek] bread, for we [have heard him saying], "It is necessary to partake of [Greek] bread." But it was not Error which spoke through him. Again he (Mani) points out that a date-palm tree spoke with Aianos, the Baptist from Koche, and commanded him to say to its lord: "Don't cut (me) down because my fruit is stolen, but grant me this year."

Then Sita and the group of his fellow presbyters set up a synod on Mani's account. They also summoned the master of the house, Pattikios, and said to him: 'Your son has turned aside from our Law and wishes to go into the world.' Now Pattikios said: 'Summon him yourselves.' Another said: 'Do not profane the waters.' And Mani said to them: "In no way would I [destroy the] commandments of the Savior." And also: "You, who say that you are a servant and righteous, why have you not guarded my honor?"

This is the moment when Mani became a Prophet.